

HISTORY OF UZBEK JEWELRY

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Annotation. *In this article, the origin of jewelry and the usage of the first jewelry items explores in the world during prehistory. Additionally, the spread of jewelries is analyzed in details in the Central Asia thorough same archeological manuments. The centers of Uzbek jewelry are researched with their unique characteristics.*

Key words: *Stone Age, cave-dwellers, metalworking Bactria-Margiana Archeological Complex, Sopoltera culture, stamping, Arabek, basman technique, shokila.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуется происхождение ювелирных изделий и их использование в доисторические времена. Кроме того, подробно анализируется распространение ювелирного искусства в Центральной Азии на основе археологических памятников. Также рассматриваются школы узбекского ювелирного искусства с их уникальными особенностями.*

Ключевые слова: *Каменный век, пещерные жители, металлообработка, Бактрийско-Маргианский археологический комплекс, культура Сополтепа, чеканка, Арабек, техника басма, шокила.*

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated in the *New Uzbekistan Strategy* that we must accept all stages of our history as a whole and study them comprehensively. A nation that draws strength from past achievements and victories while learning lessons from mistakes and defeats can correctly determine its path of development and future¹. We must teach our youth to learn from history, draw conclusions, and equip them with historical knowledge and historical thinking. Jewelry is considered the ancient type of applied art in the world. It is said by old masters that as long as there is at least one woman on earth, the jewelers' business will not die. The urge to decorate oneself is universal human trait, and it is likely that our early ancestors to attract partners, gain social recognition, and establish status used the basic forms of jewelry. Although no clothing from the Old Stone Age has been preserved, it is believed early humans shielded themselves from harsh weather by wearing animal skins and possibly weaving simple fibers like mammoth wool grass into covering. Unlike skin, wool, and matting materials such as stone, bone, and shell are more durable, which explains why the earliest known adornments predate the oldest surviving clothing². The museum holds simple bead made from stone, bone, and teeth crafted by cave dwellers in France and Spain during the later period of the Old Stone Age. Bone needles serve as the physical evidence of skin

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clothing that was likely wear for protection against the intense cold of stone era. From the very beginning, people wore decorative objects. Bead and pendants might have been created in the first place as charms to protect the early people or his possession from all evil powers. Additionally, small jewels would be worn for safety or convenience and would then assume decorative importance. Both clothing and ornaments must have been provided with strings, thongs of raw-hide, or real imitation thorns, the earliest pins. Strings around the head and waist, especially as the first forms of fillets and girdles that later became prominent in the history of jewelry, must have been necessary to restrain the bulky skin garments and the billowing hair of early man. While different motives may have played a role from the very beginning, even the simplest ornaments that have survived from millennia suggest that vanity, superstition, and practical considerations were always linked to an instinctive interest in color and symmetry for their own sake. Although earliest people enjoyed the rudiment of jewellery, the first usage of metals like copper did not come along after the beginnings of agriculture, which brought life in small settled communities and consequently many new discoveries. Copper was the first metal to be used by human for jewelry and agriculture tools. Copper objects were at first small and rare and were worked in much the same manner as stone, but in Mesopotamia, majority of copper tools and weapons that were found by archeologists, date back to 3500 b.c. They are the earliest known examples of advanced metalworking 3 techniques. It is still unbelievable where this knowledge was first discovered. The appear of the first metal jewelries in the Central Asia was linked with the Bactria-Margiana Archeological Complex (Turkmenistan, Uzbekiston, Afghanistan, and Tajikistan) which gets back around 2300-1700 BCE. 39 amulets and 22 stamps were found in Sopoltepa culture during the archaeological expedition. 35 of these amulets were found in the cemetery, and 4 of them were found in the spoil layer. Based on the results of this printed experiment, it is said that the archaeological artifact commonly referred to as a seal actually served the function of a seal in only a small portion of cases. The majority of these items served as rings, while others functioned as marks, symbols, and emblems. Although the design and shape of objects in these categories are very similar, their functions are entirely different. While seals and marks are printing tools, rings, emblems, and symbols were created for wearing and adornment purposes. According to the new chronological date of the Sapalli culture, proposed by A.A. Askarov and Sh.B. Shaydullaev, the period of circulation of seals, tamgas, amulets, emblems, and symbols began in the third millennium BC³. All of them were decorated with floral, geometric, animals and birds motifs such as square, snake and eagle images. Jewelry is an important interial part of uzbek customes and it has a deep history like ceramics and hand embroidery.

During tymurid dynasty, jewelry items were well-established like other folk arts. Typically, palace' high classes and amirs played important role in the development of this craft because of significant demand. After invading other countries, Amur Temur always gave orders to collect all best masters including jewelers and offer them visit Samarkand and other cities. As a result, jewelry-making flourished in Samarkand and Herat. Different types of jewelry and valuable items were made from gold, silver, and copper

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alloys. The number of skilled jewelers who applied fine artistic craftsmanship with delicate taste increased, and naturally, their work was especially valued by members of the ruling class. Tumor ruby is a great example of developed jewelry art. This ruby has been preserved in the British royal jewelry collection. Also, it is well-known as Timur necklace. It is a unique spinel weighing 352.5 carat. The name of the stone comes from Timur (Tamerlane), the founder and namesake of the Timurid Empire in central Asia. Timur (1336–1405) was said to have been an early owner of the spinel, which would mean that it would have to have been mined by at least the 14th century. Timur's ownership of the stone has, however, been contested by historians.

According to the accepted classification, Uzbek jewelry items divide into head, forehead, forehead-top, ear, neck, shoulder, foot, and other types of jewelry. At the beginning of XIX century, art of jewelry fully manifested itself through its ethnographic characteristics, various forms, materials, technical methods, and types of items. Jewelry was made of gold, silver, bronze, copper and gems. Gold was used for gilding, as according to Sharia, men were forbidden to wear gold items. Gems were used – garnet, beryl, colored stones – turquoise, carnelian, and coral, pearl. Jewelry covered the woman's head, framed her face, and covered her neck⁴. In the Central Asia, the majority of jewelry was prepared from silver in the first half of the XIX century. Golden items were made only in royal palaces, mainly in the palace of the Emirate of Bukhara. Since, gold was dug in the valley of Bukhara from the ancient times. Court jewelry unlike master of other craft had a special status in Bukhara. They even received more titles and positions. On the other hand, jewelry trade belonged to the lowest classes in Khorezm. In the XIX century, several centers of jewelry developed in Uzbekistan including Bukhara, Khorezm, Tashkent, Samarkand, Kokand, Surkhandaryo, Karakalpak centers. There are different methods of traditional metal-working. For example, cutting, smithing, casting, chasing, engraving, plate and open-work filigree and stamping have been used by Uzbek jewelers since olden days. The ancient jewelers were skilled in granulating metal, gilding, inlaid work, blackening and enameling. Women wore on several jewelry sets for special holidays like wedding or visiting relatives' house. The weight of jewelry sets reached up to 5 kg. However, they usually put on bracelets and earrings in daily life for purpose of amulet.

Karakalpak jewelry art in the XIX century was a one of the major schools of art, distinguished by its ancient traditions and the influence of neighboring circles. In Karakalpakia, girls and young women's dresses richly decorated with jewels. Elderly women wore usually simple rings and earrings, while men put on buckles and plates on girdles, as well as severe rings with a single large stone or signet. Also, the head-dress of girls and young women was originally and attractively decorative. Little caps worn by girls—*tilladuzi*—were adorned with silver plates and crowned with a hollow dome. *Saukele*, a bride's helmet-shaped wedding head-dress, was trimmed with silver plates covered with abstract portrayals of sheep's heads and ear-laps consisting of rows of coral beads. There were different types of rings in Karakalpakia. *Arabek*—gold nose-rings of a round shape—were decorated with spiral curves and small hollow beads. Besides simple round and oblong earrings with various pendants, Karakalpak women wore earrings with long chains passing under the chin and falling down to the breast. These pendants ended with fringes of delicate chains with small trinkets. Karakalpak breast ornaments, such as *ongir*, were a particular kind of embroidered bib with small silver plates sewn onto them. A

⁴ Ўзбекистон халқ санъати - Албом.Т.,1978. Б-60

loop-shaped buckle was sewn onto the lower border of the bib, where keys were hung, or a small dome—*ongir monshak*—on which little silver chains with bells were suspended, tinkling with every motion. Of no less interest is the *khaikel*, a figure-shaped breast ornament of the pendant kind, engraved and ornamented with stones and chains with little bells.

Tashkent jewelry items can be judged only by the remaining samples. People from the middle class mainly wore jewelry items made of silver and additional gold alloys. Tashkent jewelry masters used the *basman* technique less often. In order to decorate objects, they widely disseminated carvings for colored glass stones, simplifying the work of the filigree. The most commonly used colors were red "cut" glass and blue "turquoise."

Khorezmian jewelry items are distinguished by their unique and unusual characteristics. Some examples of Khorezmian jewelry are well-preserved in the State Museum of Applied Arts and Handicrafts of Uzbekistan. There are various types of Khorezmian jewelry, including

Qoshina – a women's forehead decoration, and *Zebigardon* – a breast decoration with pendants. *Kalitbogy* was well known as a breast ornament among women. It was not only used for adornment but also served as a way to carry crucial keys.

The most famous jewelry item among Khorezmian women is the *shokila*, which consists of several elements, including a diadem with numerous pendants decorated with multicolored enamel, temple pendants, and two or three necklaces of different lengths worn under the chin, on the neck, and across the chest. By the end of the 20th century, these elements became separate pieces, and both the temple-chest piece and the forehead-temple piece were referred to as *shokila*.

Jewelers used various precious stones to decorate jewelry, each carrying its own symbolic meaning. For example, turquoise was a symbol of victory. Wearing necklaces made of amber and small coins was believed to protect against barrenness. Women also wore jewelry adorned with corals and cloves to maintain their beauty and a good complexion. Additionally, to ensure a husband's faithfulness, women wore coral necklaces exclusively.

In conclusion, jewelry has been well-known since the Stone Age. At that time, women wore only primitive jewelry made of stone and animal bones, believing it would protect them from evil forces. The discovery of copper, the first metal used for jewelry, marked the beginning of its artistic development. The applied art of jewelry in Central Asia dates back to the Bronze Age. Archaeologists discovered examples of ancient jewelry during excavations at the Sopoltepa site. During the Bronze Age, jewelry was not only used for personal adornment but also served as stamps for ceramics. Additionally, different cities in Uzbekistan have their own distinct jewelry styles. For example, *Haikel* is unique to Karakalpak culture, while *Shokila* is traditionally worn by Khorezmian women.

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